

ISic1502

I.Sicily inscription 1502

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

volcanic (pietra di Fuardo)

Object

stele

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Lipara

Place of origin (modern)

Lipari

Provenance

Exact findspot not known

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Lipari, Museo Archeologico

Regionale Eoliano "Luigi Bernabò Brea", inventory 12334

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI334823

1. Θ (εοῖς) Ἐπιτυμβίοις vel sim.)
2. Νεαρχίας Λειβέρας
3. ἐπόησε Νεαρχία
4. Γνωστή ἀδελφῆ.
- 5.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645003

PHI 334823

Bibliography

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